

LOW VELOCITY IMPACT MODELLING ON LAMINATE COMPOSITE: AN INDUSTRIAL APPLICATION

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ABSTRACT

Low velocity impact modelling of composite structures is carried out in the framework of virtual testing program launched at ArianeGroup to reduce experimental tests performed for qualification of composite structures. Up to now demonstration of tolerance of composite structures to damage is fully based on tests. This paper presents validation methodology of low velocity impact Finite Element modelling based on experimental test results obtained with carbon fibre reinforced PEEK composite.

The first phase of the work concerns standard tests with quasi-isotropic laminates plates. The second phase of validation followed by ArianeGroup deals with technological tests in order to be more representative to real structures. The example presented in this paper concerns the reduction of strength due to impact near a hole.

1 INTRODUCTION

It is well known that structures made of composite laminates reinforced with carbon fibre are sensitive to low velocity impacts which could occur during assembly or maintenance and also during the operating life. Damage is not often visible with carbon fibre especially when dropped objects are not sharp. Damage tolerance design of composite structure is based on experimental approach and tests on scale-one structure have to be performed to prove there are able to sustain extreme loads.

The objective followed by ArianeGroup in the framework of virtual testing program is to limit the number of tests which have to be done to justify the acceptance of low velocity impact damage thanks to advanced finite element model enabling prediction of damage and the residual strength and recently available at ArianeGroup.

The most critical damages are delamination and fibre breakage. These damages are particularly severe because they drastically reduce residual mechanical characteristics of structures for launchers mainly loaded in compression. Several solutions can be used to enhance impact damage resistance of composite by using interlocked fibrous architecture, to use tough interleaves, to use tough matrix or to optimize lay-up sequence. High-performance thermoplastic resins are chosen because of their higher toughnesses compared to advanced thermoset resin which are doped with thermoplastic charges.

This study is dealing with carbon fibre/PEEK laminate and the objective was to be able to simulate damage due to impact and to predict the residual strength.

The first aspect of the work concerns standard tests with quasi-isotropic laminates plates. The second phase of validation followed by ArianeGroup deals with technological tests to be more representative to real structures. The example presented in this paper concerns the reduction of strength due to impact near a hole.

2 IMPACT DAMAGE SIMULATION

To capture the effects of progressive damage and failure on laminated composite structures, failure modes in both fibre and matrix resin are considered. The model considers fibre failure in tension and compression, matrix cracking taking into account permanent indentation and delamination. It is based on the use of cohesive zone models to capture delamination between plies of different orientations and transverse matrix cracking in plies.

The model has been developed and improved by Bouvet and al and implemented into Explicit/Dynamic Abaqus code with a VUMAT subroutine [1-3]. This “discrete ply model” is able to simulate the complex three-dimensional damage patterns and the residual indent depth let by the indenter (Fig. 1). This information is important for damage tolerance analysis based on BVID (Barely Visible Impact Damage). The Explicit/Dynamic model needs several material characteristics at ply level and at fibre one. Some are determined via standard tests and some are very specific like mean crushing stress and fibre critical energy release rate.

Figure 1: Principle of the “Discrete Ply Model”

3 DETERMINATION OF THE STRAIN ENERGY RELEASE RATE IN SHEAR

It is well known that majority of the energy absorbed in laminate during impact dissipates into delamination propagation in shear mode (mode II). Therefore, the critical Energy Release Rate in mode II (GIIc) is a key parameter.

Some authors show that critical Energy Release Rate changes with the velocity of the crack growth. It is particularly the case for interlaminar shear fracture [4-6]. Friedrich et al performed End Notched Flexure (ENF) tests at room temperature over a range of crosshead speeds from $4.2 \cdot 10^{-6}$ m/s to $9.2 \cdot 10^{-2}$ m/s and showed APC-2 composite (PEEK resin reinforced with AS4 carbon fibre) fracture toughness in mode II decreases from 1.9 N/mm to 0.4 N/mm when the crack growth velocity increases [4] They explained that APC-2 material exhibits ductile crack growth at low rates and brittle crack growth at high rates. Contrary to these results, Berger and Cantwell [7] found that interlaminar fracture toughness of APC-2 increased with crosshead displacement rate. They used a double ENF test and evaluated that G_{IIc} increases from 2.2 N/mm to 2.7 N/mm for crosshead displacement rate from $1.7 \cdot 10^{-6}$ m/s to $8.3 \cdot 10^{-3}$ m/s. They concluded that mode II interlaminar fracture toughness is strongly influenced by the yield stress of PEEK resin which varies with loading rate.

More recently Garcia Perez has determined G_{IIc} of Carbon fibre/PEEK composite via End Notched Flexure (ENF) tests and a new method based on Short Beam Shear tests (SBS) on $(0_2/90_4/0_2)$ laminate [8]. With SBS test, delamination is initiated by transverse crack in 90° ply and unstable delamination propagation is generated. Crack speed of about 1000m/s has been measured at low cross head speed (0.2 mm/s) and at high cross head speed (1 m/s) [8]. Infrared thermography has been used to calculate the energy release (G_{IIc}) according to the methodology developed by Teddy Lisle to measure fibre toughness in compression [9].

The author has found G_{IIc} is lower for unstable crack propagation for both ENF and SBS tests as synthesized in Table 1.

Test method	GIIc stable propagation N/mm	GIIc unstable propagation N/mm
ENF – Compliance method	1.3 – 2.7	<1.3
ENF – Thermography method	1.9 - 3	0.76 – 1.5
SBS- Thermography method	/	0.9 – 1,7

Table 1: Synthesis of G_{IIc} measures of Carbon fibre/PEEK [8]

4 METHODOLOGY OF LOW VELOCITY IMPACT MODEL VALIDATION

The first step of validation of the model concerns impact test campaign followed by compression after impact for different stacking sequences and impact energies with test samples defined according to ASTM D7137 standard (Fig. 2).

Comparison between experiments and simulations is based on:

- evolution of impact load with time or with displacement which is the deflection of the plate measured on the opposite side of the impact location,
- the residual depth of the indent after impact,
- composite damage after impact,
- residual strength after impact and
- mode of failure

Figure 2: Illustration of impact and compression after impacts test according to ASTM D7137

From an industrial point of view, it is necessary to enlarge the validation domain of the model by considering other stacking sequences, designs and boundary conditions.

Different cases are planned in the validation program followed by ArianeGroup:

- composite structure with an open hole and where impact damage is close to the hole
- prediction of the rupture in combined loading condition,
- composite structure with non-constant thickness and where impact damage is located in transition zone,
- composite structure with stiffeners where impact damage is close to the stiffener.

This paper only presents the results obtained on flat panel with an hole.

5 DETERMINATION OF THE MODEL PARAMETERS

If most of the parameters of the model listed in Table 2 can be determined with standardized tests. Mean crushing stress (σ_0), Fiber critical energy release rate in tension (G_{ft}) and in compression (G_{fc}) are more difficult to obtain. From an industrial point of view, these tests require deep analysis and specific computation which are not linked to standards.

These parameters have not been determined for this material but taken from literature [10-12]. Interface critical energy release rate in mode II (G_{IIc}) come from the PhD work recently published by Gracia Perez [8].

The preliminary study has been carried out with quasi-isotropic material $(0_2/45_2/90_2/-45_2)_2s$ where it has been shown that simulation of the impact load versus deflection of the testsample cannot fit the experimental curve with G_{IIc} value (2.7 N/mm) usually determined with ENF method in stable crack propagation conditions (ASTM D7905). This is illustrated with Figure 3 where the best fit is obtained with G_{IIc} equal to 0.75 N/mm. The simulation reproduced quite well load drops generated by

progressive delamination of the plies. This $GIIc$ value is close to the experimental one determined for unstable propagation (Table 1).

Symbol	Parameter of the Discrete Ply Model	Test method
ρ	Density	ASTM D792
E_{lt}	Tensile Young's modulus in fiber direction (MPa)	ASTM D3039
E_{lc}	Compressive Young's modulus in fiber direction (MPa)	ASTM D3410
E_t	Transverse Young modulus (MPa)	ASTM D3039
ν	Poisson's ratio	ASTM D3039
G_{lt}	Shear modulus (MPa)	ASTM D3518
G_{tz}	Shear modulus (MPa)	ASTM D3518
S_n	Transverse failure stress (MPa)	ASTM D3039
S_t	Interlaminar shear failure stress (MPa)	ASTM D-2344
σ_0	Mean crushing stress (MPa)	[10]
ϵ_{0t}	Tensile strain in fiber direction at damage initiation	ASTM D3039
ϵ_{0c}	Compressive strain in fiber direction at damage initiation	ASTM D3410
G_{Ic}	Interface critical energy release rate in mode I (N/mm)	ASTM D5528
G_{IIc}	Interface critical energy release rate in mode II (N/mm)	[8]
G_{ft}	Fiber critical energy release rate in traction (N/mm)	[11, 12]
G_{fc}	Fiber critical energy release rate in compression (N/mm)	[11, 12]

Table 2: Synthesis of material properties needed for impact and residual strength computation

$G_{IIc} = 2.7$ N/mm (red line) ; $G_{IIc} = 0.75$ N/mm (black line)

Figure 3: Comparison simulation/experience of impact test at 20J - Influence of G_{IIc} value

Therefore, simulations of impact and compression after impact presented in this paper have been done with the same material dataset and with G_{IIc} equal to 0.75 N/mm.

Comparison between simulation and experimental results obtained with $(0_2/45_2/90_2/-45_2)_{2s}$.test samples impacted at 20 joules shows the relevance of the model to provide crucial information for composite structure justification which addresses the size of the damage, the residual indent after impact and finally the residual compression strength (Fig. 4). Experimental displacement is determined with the measure of the acceleration of the indenter and the simulation gives directly the displacement of the indenter.

Figure 4: Experimental results and simulation obtained with $(0_2/45_2/90_2/-45_2)_{2s}$, impact at 20 J.

Residual indentation is not well predicted even if the model takes into account closure coefficient to simulate transverse crack closure. This coefficient has been taken from literature making the assumption of residual closure of about 30% of the full crack opening [13]. Prediction of the strength in compression after impact is fair for designer because our objectives are to have relevant and conservative predictions.

6 VALIDATION OF THE MODEL

In order to reduce the number of impact tests for structure qualification with respect to damage tolerance issue, simulations must be efficient in terms of relevance of the damage prediction and the prediction of the residual strength with conservatism.

6.1) Impact tests on plates

Plates with the three stacking sequences have been impacted at 10, 20 and 30 joules and tested in compression afterwards.

Experimental results and prediction of the projected surface delamination, permanent indentation after the impact and residual strength in compression are presented in Table 3. The relative error is calculated with simulation result as reference.

Several observations can be made:

- projected delamination area is overestimated with the model for $(45_2/-45_2/0_2/90_2)_{2s}$ sequence,
- no discriminate results have been obtained for permanent indentation after impact for the three stacking sequences. Nevertheless simulation predicts increasing residual deformation with increasing impact energy,
- experiment and simulation results show reduction of residual strength in compression with increasing impact energy.

stacking sequence		10 joules	20 joules	30 joules
$(0_2/45_2/90_2/-45_2)_{2s}$	Experimental	696	2645	5163
	Simulation	776	1829	5013
	Relative error%	+11	-31	-3
$(45_2/-45_2/0_2/90_2)_{2s}$	Experimental	636	1731	3452
	Simulation	765	1822	3952
	Relative error%	+20	+5	+15
$(90_2/-45_2/0_2/45_2)_{2s}$	Experimental	560	3262	5393
	Simulation	865	2957	4806
	Relative error%	+55	-9	-11

Projected delamination area (mm²)

stacking sequence		10 joules	20 joules	30 joules
$(0_2/45_2/90_2/-45_2)_{2s}$	Experimental	0.25	0.29	0.34
	Simulation	0.20	0.33	0.44
	Relative error%	-21	+15	+28
$(45_2/-45_2/0_2/90_2)_{2s}$	Experimental	0.23	0.34	0.38
	Simulation	0.16	0.32	/
	Relative error%	-32	-6	/
$(90_2/-45_2/0_2/45_2)_{2s}$	Experimental	0.24	0.33	0.35
	Simulation	0.16	0.32	0.43
	Relative error%	-32	-3	+21

Permanent indentation after the impact in the impact area (mm)

stacking sequence		10 joules	20 joules	30 joules
$(0_2/45_2/90_2/-45_2)_{2s}$	Experimental	273	263	212
	Simulation	361	277	217
	Relative error%	+33	+6	+2
$(45_2/-45_2/0_2/90_2)_{2s}$	Experimental	262	240	219
	Simulation	335	290	227
	Relative error%	+28	+21	+4
$(90_2/-45_2/0_2/45_2)_{2s}$	Experimental	271	239	216
	Simulation	341	278	228
	Relative error%	+26	+17	+5

Residual compression strength (MPa)

Table 3: Synthesis of experiment and simulation of impact damage and residual strength in compression of carbon fibre/PEEK

Previous validation of the low-velocity impact model used in this study has been performed by Hongkarnjanakul and al with carbon fibre reinforced epoxy resin [14]. They studied the influence of staking sequence for 8-double plies, mirror symmetric, quasi-isotropic laminated plates. A comparison of impact damage patterns with thermoset and thermoplastic composites can be achieved because of the similarities with lay-up sequences, plate thickness (around 4mm), size of the plate (150 mm*100 mm) and impact test conditions (ASTM D7137 – ϕ 16 mm indenter of 2 kg). Mean crushing stress (σ_0), Fiber critical energy release rate in traction (Gft) and in compression (Gfc) are similar for both simulation with thermoset and thermoplastic composites. They come from tests performed on carbon fibre/epoxy resin composite. Ply rupture in compression is due to complex phenomena combining local fibre buckling, crushing and kinking bands mechanisms and it is difficult to quantify fibre critical energy release rate in compression Gfc. Lisle [9] via thermography investigation and Hongkarnjanakul [14] via simulation have found the same order of magnitude around 40 N/mm, value taken in the simulations.

It is important to mention here an important point which addresses the significant difference of the interface critical energy release rate in mode II for thermoset composite compared to thermoplastic composite which is respectively 2.1 N/mm and 0.75 mm.

Comparison of the size and the shape of delamination areas obtained experimentally and by simulation for the two composite materials is presented in Figure 5.

One can observe for both cases, the relevance of the model to predict the shape of projected delamination. The shape is influenced by the orientation of the external ply located on the opposite side of the impact for T700GC/M21 composite. With carbon fibre/PEEK delamination pattern doesn't seem to be influenced by the orientation of the external ply with quasi-isotropic laminate. Contrary to thermoset composite observations, larger sizes of delamination are located in the middle of the plates in agreement with simulation.

Figure 5: Comparison between experimental and numerical ultrasonic C-Scan for delamination of T700GC/M21 and Carbon fibre/PEEK after impact

Therefore we can conclude the explicit finite element model implemented in Abaqus software gives relevant information of impact damage and residual strength in compression. From a designer point of view the relative difference between simulation and experiment of less than 20% is acceptable since there are many factors affecting damage results such as the uncertainties in G_{ft} , G_{fc} , parameters not characterized in this study. The same order of relative error has been stated by Hongkarnjanakul and al with T700GC/M21 [14].

Nevertheless, we also highlight that predictions of residual strength in compression for all the tests with carbon fibre/PEEK are not conservative in the sense they overestimate the experimental results.

This is stated even if prediction of delamination can be greater than experimental one as illustrated with $(45_2/-45_2/0_2/90_2)_2s$ stacking sequence.

Therefore more work has to be done to quantify scattering of the most sensitive parameters of the model as it is actually done for any computation of composite structure.

6.2) Impact tests on plate with hole

The second step of validation was to introduce specific boundary conditions encountered when impact is generated near the edge of a hole. The objective was to know if damage near a hole can increase the reduction of residual strength in compression and shear.

The stacking sequence is in this case more complex with a non-isotropic material $[90_2/-45/0/45_2/0/-45_2/0/45_2/-45]_s$. The size of the panel is 300 mm*200 mm with 60mm hole diameter located at the center (Fig. 6). Simulation has been performed to define the position of the impact and the energy. The position of the impact has been chosen to not generate too much damage due to interaction with the hole. Finally impact energy of 20J at 20mm from the edge with simple supported condition has been fixed. The panel was laying on 275mm*175mm metallic frame.

Simulation predicts lower surface delamination (680 mm^2) at 20J compared to previous test with 1500mm*100mm plates (1800 mm^2 - 2960 mm^2), mainly due to higher flexibility of the panel (higher ration length over thickness) and the impact load is also lower.

Simulation also predicts delamination growing towards the edge of the hole (Fig. 6).

Figure 6 : Simulation of impact damage near hole

Prediction of the residual strength in compression has been done and reveals that 20 joules damage will not reduce residual strength in compression compared to the panel with hole and without impact damage. Same conclusion is reached with shear test where failure is generated by cross shape damage which doesn't interact with impact damage. Stress curves are superposed (Fig. 7).

Figure 7 : Simulation of compression and in-plane shear after impact

Validation of these simulations with experimental tests has been launched and first investigations have been done by Garcia Perez during his thesis [8]. He found quite good results, confirming this model can reproduce the level of impact load seen by the panel and the interaction with impact damage and edge effect of the hole creating local splinter (Fig. 8).

Garcia Perez measured an average projected delamination area of 890mm² which is higher than simulation. He found that 20J impact near the edge of the hole didn't reduce the residual strength in compression compared to the same panel without the hole which is in accordance with simulation. Unfortunately prediction of the residual strength is overestimate the experience. Compression after impact of large panel was quite difficult to master because of buckling problem met during the test even if specific anti-buckling device was designed thanks to preliminary simulation.

Therefore more work has to be done to better matter the behaviors of large panels and in parallel complementary simulations with more adapted boundaries conditions are required to be more efficient to predict residual strength with impact damage.

Figure 8: Experimental results [8]

7 CONCLUSION

This study has allowed making a significant step toward the objective followed by ArianeGroup to predict impact damage and residual strength of laminated composite materials.

The explicit finite element model is now implemented in industrial environment. This study shows that if this model gives a fair representation of phenomena observed experimentally, more work is still necessary to reach the industrial validation which consists in making predictions with a certain level of relevance of conservatism.

Therefore it is necessary to perform complementary tests to better estimate the most critical parameters of the model, to repeat impact tests at different levels of energy, different lay-up sequences, to better estimate experimental scattering and last but not least to pursue with technology tests knowing that performance of relevant mechanical tests on big panels is complex, needs efficient computation strategy to reduce cpu time and by the end needs a significant budget. For sure with this investment, such tool will be able to reduce the number of costly tests generally requested by the damage tolerance analysis, a non-negligible part of composite structure qualification program.

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